

Influence of Lizard Fright on Urine Bilirubin Level

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ABSTRACT

The basic intention behind this study is to check any influence of lizard fright on the concentration of bilirubin within urine. Many subjects participated in this study. Many persons possessed lizard aversion but there is no possibility of any relation between both of them.

Keywords: Insects, Red blood cells, Lizard fright.

1. Introduction

Bilirubin is the yellowish substance that occurs when the red blood cells start degenerating. Its higher concentration can lead to several infectious diseases like jaundice and yellowing of eyes. It is released in liver in case of any liver infection. This compound then released into urine.

Herpetophobia is basically the fear from lizards. Lizards are house found reptiles. They usually appear during night time. They used to eat small insects present on walls. But they are not deadly for human beings, but still some persons get feared from them due to their personal reason. They were suffering from this type of phobia. The scientific worker has already been correlate different parameters of a specific topic [1-2].

The aim for this study is to observe any impact of lizard aversion on the presence of bilirubin in urine.

2. Materials and Methods

The study was compiled by the survey among many subjects to analyze the impact of lizard's fear to urine bilirubin level. Urine bilirubin content can be measured by urinalysis test. This test gives different values which show that either blood bilirubin is present in our urine or absent there.

Mathematical Calculation

This was done by using MSTAT.

3. Results and Discussions

The results for this work have been given in the table. This table showed that the influence of lizard fright on the concentration of bilirubin in urine.

Gender	Lizard fright	Brave person
Male	50	50
Female	65.71	34.28

4. Conclusion

More than 50% of persons get feared from lizard but the influence of this fear on presence of bilirubin within urine is not possible. The scientific worker has already been correlate different parameters of a specific topic [3-4].

Declarations

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Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional, or personal interests.

Ethical Approval

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan.

Consent for publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this research work.

Availability of data and material

The authors are willing to share the data and material according to relevant needs.

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